

All Multi-fold preprint papers, as of April 1, 2023

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April 1, 2023

Abstract:

As it will take a while to have all papers captured in the multi-fold theory repository [1], this document lists them as of April 1, 2023, when the repository was created.

1. List

The list is extracted from [2] and [3]. A few papers not be “multi-fold related”. We ask the reader for forgiveness.

We expect these papers to progressively, with time, be made available on [1].

Note many papers may not yet have been published on [2,3]. They can all be found on [4].

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[viXra.org](https://vixra.org) > Stephane H. Maes

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[75] [viXra:2303.0161](https://vixra.org/2303.0161) submitted on 2023-03-29 21:41:09 , (20 unique-IP downloads)

Multi-folds in Yang Mills Feynman Diagrams

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[74] [viXra:2303.0154](https://vixra.org/2303.0154) submitted on 2023-03-28 00:55:02 , (10 unique-IP downloads)

Review of the Multi-fold Theory Principles and the SM_G

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[73] [viXra:2303.0114](https://vixra.org/2303.0114) submitted on 2023-03-19 02:54:57 , (19 unique-IP downloads)

Multi-Fold Gravity and Double Copy of Gauge Theory

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[72] [viXra:2303.0031](https://vixra.org/2303.0031) replaced on 2023-03-21 04:45:08 , (31 unique-IP downloads)

Yeah or Nay on Black Holes as Explanation for Dark Energy?

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[71] [viXra:2303.0025](https://vixra.org/2303.0025) submitted on 2023-03-05 04:10:59 , (56 unique-IP downloads)

Trans-Planckian Censorship Conjecture: Factual in Multi-fold Universes as well as GR Universes

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[70] [viXra:2302.0129](https://vixra.org/2302.0129) submitted on 2023-02-24 18:39:45 , (99 unique-IP downloads)

Deriving the Multi-fold Theory from General Relativity at Planck scale

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[69] [viXra:2302.0108](#) submitted on 2023-02-21 19:00:59 , (74 unique-IP downloads)

From Quantum Relational Equivalence to Multi-Folds Encounter in the Real Universe and Confirmation of the E/g Conjecture

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[68] [viXra:2301.0155](#) submitted on 2023-01-31 01:10:29 , (83 unique-IP downloads)

Gravitational Bootstrap, S-matrix, Superstrings, and The Plausible Unphysicality of Gravitons

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[67] [viXra:2301.0036](#) submitted on 2023-01-06 00:32:50 , (111 unique-IP downloads)

Oops For The Loops II: Real Oops; LQG Does Not Optimize the Hilbert Einstein Action

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[66] [viXra:2212.0206](#) submitted on 2022-12-29 22:22:57 , (105 unique-IP downloads)

Multi-folds, The Fruit From The Loops? Fixing "Oops for The Loops" May Encounter Multi-folds in General Relativity And The E/G Conjecture

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[65] [viXra:2212.0168](#) replaced on 2022-12-29 23:54:32 , (82 unique-IP downloads)

Oops For The Loops: Mounting LQG Woes And A Challenge To The LQG Community

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[64] [viXra:2212.0120](#) submitted on 2022-12-11 21:32:00 , (171 unique-IP downloads)

Multi-Fold Embeddings, Spacetime Matter Induction or Gravity Asymptotically Safe and the Ads/cft Correspondence Conjecture, They All Can Recover the Standard Model

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[63] [viXra:2212.0037](#) submitted on 2022-12-04 20:42:59 , (154 unique-IP downloads)

Multi-fold Non-Commutative Spacetime, Higgs and The Standard Model with Gravity

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[62] [viXra:2211.0173](#) submitted on 2022-11-30 04:45:10 , (129 unique-IP downloads)

Right-Handed Neutrinos and Traversable Wormholes: the Key to Entanglement, Gravity and Multi-Folds Extensions to Er=epr?

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[61] [viXra:2211.0154](#) submitted on 2022-11-27 04:55:44 , (53 unique-IP downloads)

Co2 and CH4 Absorption Powered by Nuclear Fusion, Via Fission, is the Only Way to Manage Climate Change and the Planet's Trigger Points

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Climate Research](#)

[60] [viXra:2211.0150](#) submitted on 2022-11-25 23:48:50 , (35 unique-IP downloads)

Super Cloud or Meta Cloud: A Problematic Approach

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Data Structures and Algorithms](#)

[59] [viXra:2211.0100](#) submitted on 2022-11-17 23:14:33, (178 unique-IP downloads)

Multi-fold Gravity-Electroweak Theory and Symmetry Breaking

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[58] [viXra:2211.0001](#) submitted on 2022-11-01 00:59:45 , (104 unique-IP downloads)

Spacetime and Gravity Are 2D Around Planck Scales: a Universal Property of Consistent Quantum Gravity

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[57] [viXra:2210.0081](#) submitted on 2022-10-18 23:43:26 , (100 unique-IP downloads)

Pointers to Nowhere with Geometric Unity Theory, or Some Ways Forward in Multi-fold Universes?

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[56] [viXra:2210.0004](#) submitted on 2022-10-01 19:57:36 , (162 unique-IP downloads)

More on Multi-fold Particles as Microscopic Black Holes with Higgs Regularizing Extremality and Singularities

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[55] [viXra:2208.0151](#) submitted on 2022-08-28 17:44:01 , (230 unique-IP downloads)

Quantum Gravity Asymptotic Safety from 2D Universal Regime and Smooth Transition to Dual Superstrings

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[54] [viXra:2208.0082](#) submitted on 2022-08-15 00:54:29 , (171 unique-IP downloads)

A Multi-fold Universe Genesis Inspired By Explosive Total Collision: The Source Of The Big Bang?

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[53] [viXra:2208.0078](#) submitted on 2022-08-13 08:27:50 , (246 unique-IP downloads)

The String Swampland and de Sitter Vacua: A Consistent Perspective for Superstrings and Multi-fold Universes

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[52] [viXra:2208.0009](#) submitted on 2022-08-03 00:23:50 , (128 unique-IP downloads)

Different Approaches to Compute Hawking Black Holes Decay

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[51] [viXra:2207.0174](#) submitted on 2022-07-30 21:37:37, (134 unique-IP downloads)

Entangled Neural Networks from Multi-fold Universes to Biology

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[50] [viXra:2207.0172](#) submitted on 2022-07-29 03:02:09 , (260 unique-IP downloads)

What is the Multi-fold Theory? Its Main Characteristics in a Few Words

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[49] [viXra:2207.0118](#) submitted on 2022-07-17 03:26:29 , (211 unique-IP downloads)

The W-type Multi-Fold Hypothesis and The Quantum Physics Interpretation of Wave Functions and QFT

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[48] [viXra:2207.0049](#) submitted on 2022-07-06 19:05:22, (106 unique-IP downloads)

Itsm and Esm in the Bigger World. Separation of Concerns: a Modern Approach of Itil for the Enterprise

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Data Structures and Algorithms](#)

[47] [viXra:2205.0143](#) submitted on 2022-05-29 22:14:57, (222 unique-IP downloads)

Viable Lattice Spacetime and Absence of Quantum Gravitational Anomalies in a Multi-fold Universe

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[46] [viXra:2204.0152](#) replaced on 2022-08-21 17:29:12 , (267 unique-IP downloads)

Can Chirality Flips Occur in a Multi-Fold Universe? What About Conservation Laws II?

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[45] [viXra:2204.0146](#) submitted on 2022-04-23 23:39:45, (233 unique-IP downloads)

Multi-fold Higgs Fields and Bosons

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[44] [viXra:2112.0144](#) submitted on 2021-12-27 18:13:14, (361 unique-IP downloads)

The Multi-fold Theory: A Synopsis

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[43] [viXra:2111.0144](#) replaced on 2021-12-28 19:06:08, (232 unique-IP downloads)

How the $er = Epr$, $GR = QM$ and Ads/cft Correspondence Conjectures, Can be Explained in Multi-Fold Theory, Along with the E/g Conjecture. a Call to the Physics Community!

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[42] [viXra:2111.0071](#) submitted on 2021-11-14 19:34:25, (274 unique-IP downloads)

Particles of The Standard Model In Multi-Fold Universes

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[41] [viXra:2107.0143](#) replaced on 2022-10-25 04:09:50 , (225 unique-IP downloads)

Invalidating Cantor's Continuum Hypothesis and Solving Hilbert's #1 Problem II

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Set Theory and Logic](#)

[40] [viXra:2105.0136](#) submitted on 2021-05-23 12:30:41, (235 unique-IP downloads)

Multi-Fold Black Holes: Entropy, Evolution and Quantum Extrema

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[39] [viXra:2105.0042](#) submitted on 2021-05-08 22:31:12, (230 unique-IP downloads)

Multi-Fold Universe Dark Matter Effects Survive Low-Mass Galaxies with Dark Matter Deficits and Excesses

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[38] [viXra:2105.0041](#) submitted on 2021-05-08 23:09:55, (207 unique-IP downloads)

Multi-Fold Dark Matter Effects and Early Supermassive Black Holes

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[37] [viXra:2105.0013](#) submitted on 2021-05-04 21:27:11, (119 unique-IP downloads)

The Multi-Fold Theory: a Synopsis so Far

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[36] [viXra:2104.0030](#) submitted on 2021-04-07 23:25:42, (259 unique-IP downloads)

A Bold Prediction on the Muon Anomalous Magnetic Moment, and Expected Resulted to be Published on April 7, 2021 by the Fermilab Muon G-2, and Its Explanation

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[35] [viXra:2103.0202](#) submitted on 2021-03-30 23:33:06, (310 unique-IP downloads)

No Conventional Sterile Neutrinos in a Multi-Fold Universe: Just SMG Business as Usual

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[34] [viXra:2103.0195](#) submitted on 2021-03-31 16:49:27, (343 unique-IP downloads)

Circular Arguments in String and Superstring Theory from a Multi-fold Universe Perspective

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[33] [viXra:2103.0191](#) submitted on 2021-03-30 02:41:57, (236 unique-IP downloads)

New Physics with LHCb to Explain Loss of Lepton Universality, or Just Gravity?

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [High Energy Particle Physics](#)

[32] [viXra:2103.0142](#) submitted on 2021-03-21 00:06:07, (171 unique-IP downloads)

“Quantum Gravity Emergence from Entanglement in a Multi-Fold Universe”: 2D or 2+1D Spacetime at Small Scales

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[31] [viXra:2103.0091](#) submitted on 2021-03-13 18:18:03, (49 unique-IP downloads)

Latest Highlights and Results From Multi-Fold Models

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[30] [viXra:2102.0137](#) submitted on 2021-02-22 17:34:24, (329 unique-IP downloads)

Renormalization and Asymptotic Safety of Gravity in a Multi-Fold Universe: More Tracking of the Standard Model at the Cost of Supersymmetries, GUTs and Superstrings

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[29] [viXra:2102.0079](#) submitted on 2021-02-15 19:44:49, (230 unique-IP downloads)

Multi-Fold Universe Dark Matter Successful Explanation and the “Too Thin Universe” but “Too Strong Gravity Lensing by Galaxy Clusters”

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[28] [viXra:2012.0197](#) submitted on 2020-12-27 02:04:22, (196 unique-IP downloads)

Interpretation of “Neural Network as the World”

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[27] [viXra:2012.0191](#) submitted on 2020-12-26 11:57:34, (171 unique-IP downloads)

Implicit Multi-Fold Mechanisms in a Neural Network Model of the Universe

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[26] [viXra:2012.0152](#) submitted on 2020-12-20 20:19:47, (134 unique-IP downloads)

No Gravity Superposition Induced Wave Function Collapse in a Multi-fold Universe

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[25] [viXra:2011.0208](#) submitted on 2020-11-30 09:05:18, (273 unique-IP downloads)

Tracking Down the Standard Model with Gravity in Multi-Fold Universes

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[24] [viXra:2010.0207](#) submitted on 2020-10-25 12:18:24, (253 unique-IP downloads)

Area Laws Between Multi-Fold Universes and AdS

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[23] [viXra:2010.0155](#) submitted on 2020-10-19 22:04:03, (212 unique-IP downloads)

Multi-fold Gravitons In-N-Out Spacetime

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[22] [viXra:2010.0140](#) submitted on 2020-10-18 19:57:58, (277 unique-IP downloads)

Superstrings Encounters of the Second, Third or Fourth Types?

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[21] [viXra:2010.0139](#) submitted on 2020-10-18 19:58:12, (333 unique-IP downloads)

The E/g Conjecture: Entanglement is Gravity and Gravity is Entanglement

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[20] [viXra:2010.0133](#) submitted on 2020-10-18 12:24:03, (189 unique-IP downloads)

Particles, Especially Virtual Particles, in a Multi-fold Universe vs. QFT

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[19] [viXra:2010.0121](#) replaced on 2021-04-08 22:17:19, (303 unique-IP downloads)

More Matter Than Antimatter, All Falling Down

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[18] [viXra:2010.0095](#) submitted on 2020-10-14 19:06:28, (250 unique-IP downloads)

Massless and Massive Multi-Gravity in a Multi-fold Universe

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[17] [viXra:2010.0090](#) submitted on 2020-10-13 20:15:39, (271 unique-IP downloads)

Derivation of the Equivalence Principle in a Multi-Fold Universe

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[16] [viXra:2010.0083](#) submitted on 2020-10-11 22:18:50, (159 unique-IP downloads)

Entanglement and Random Walks Concretize Time in a Multi-fold Universe

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[15] [viXra:2010.0032](#) submitted on 2020-10-05 21:22:17, (154 unique-IP downloads)

No Gravity Shield in Multi-folds Universes

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[14] [viXra:2010.0010](#) submitted on 2020-10-03 12:47:20, (358 unique-IP downloads)

Gravity-Like Attractions and Fluctuations Between Entangled Systems?

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[13] [viXra:2007.0173](#) submitted on 2020-07-21 18:04:56, (267 unique-IP downloads)

Gravity Stabilizes Electroweak Vacuum – No Bubble of Nothing to Worry About!

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[12] [viXra:2007.0068](#) submitted on 2020-07-12 11:10:17, (266 unique-IP downloads)

Gravity Dictates the Number of Fermion Generations: 3

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[11] [viXra:2007.0025](#) submitted on 2020-07-05 13:34:11, (284 unique-IP downloads)

Strong CP Violation Tamed in The Presence of Gravity

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[10] [viXra:2007.0018](#) submitted on 2020-07-03 10:43:14, (328 unique-IP downloads)

Right-Handed Neutrinos? Mass? Ask Gravity

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[9] [viXra:2007.0006](#) submitted on 2020-07-01 19:07:15, (354 unique-IP downloads)

Explaining Dark Matter Without New Physics?

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[8] [viXra:2006.0261](#) submitted on 2020-06-29 10:47:56, (342 unique-IP downloads)

Explaining Dark Energy, Small Cosmological Constant and Inflation Without New Physics?

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[7] [viXra:2006.0229](#) submitted on 2020-06-25 14:06:22, (348 unique-IP downloads)

Alignments and Gaps Between Multi-fold Universes And Loop Quantum Gravity

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[6] [viXra:2006.0211](#) submitted on 2020-06-22 21:50:00, (407 unique-IP downloads)

Ultimate Unification: Gravity-led Democracy vs. Uber-Symmetries

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[5] [viXra:2006.0190](#) replaced on 2022-08-22 05:41:43 , (323 unique-IP downloads)

Gravity or Magnetic Monopoles? You Cannot Have Both! II

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[4] [viXra:2006.0178](#) submitted on 2020-06-18 15:07:49, (396 unique-IP downloads)

Dualities or Analogies Between Superstrings and Multi-Fold Universes

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[3] [viXra:2006.0155](#) submitted on 2020-06-16 21:38:05, (288 unique-IP downloads)

Progress on Proving the Mass Gap for Yang Mills and Gravity (Maybe It's Already Proven...)

Authors: [Stephane H Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[2] [viXra:2006.0128](#) submitted on 2020-06-14 19:07:44, (333 unique-IP downloads)

Gravity Induced Anomalies Smearing in Standard Model so that Protons May Never Decay, Except in Black Holes

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

[1] [viXra:2006.0088](#) replaced on 2022-11-09 23:12:19 , (871 unique-IP downloads)

Quantum Gravity Emergence from Entanglement in a Multi-Fold Universe

Authors: [Stephane H. Maes](#)

Category: [Quantum Gravity and String Theory](#)

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Third-Party Links:

OSF papers (osf.io/qdaj9 and <https://osf.io/rk3vj/>) as of 4/1/23:

[Direction of Possible Multi-folds Corrections to the W Boson Mass](#)

[Entangled Neural Networks from Multi-fold Universes to Biology](#)

[New Physics is often not so new](#)

[The W-type Multi-Fold Hypothesis and The Quantum Physics Interpretation of Wave Functions and QFT](#)

[Multi-folds in Yang Mills Feynman Diagrams](#)

[Viable Lattice Spacetime and Absence of Quantum Gravitational Anomalies in a Multi-fold Universe](#)

[Hints of Multi-fold Dark Matter Effects in the Universe](#)

[Multi-fold gravity and double copy of gauge theory](#)

[Multi-fold Higgs Fields and Bosons](#)

[Multi-Fold Black Holes: Entropy, Evolution and Quantum Extrema](#)

[The E/G conjecture: entanglement is gravity and gravity is entanglement](#)

[Multi-Fold Dark Matter Effects and Early Supermassive Black Holes](#)

[Multi-Fold Universe Dark Matter Effects Survive Low-Mass Galaxies with Dark Matter Deficits and Excesses](#)

[Circular Arguments in String and Superstring Theory from a Multi-fold Universe Perspective](#)

[New Physics with LHCb to explain loss of lepton universality, or just gravity?](#)

[No Conventional Sterile Neutrinos In a Multi-fold Universe: just SMG business as usual](#)

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[Gravity or Magnetic Monopoles? You Cannot Have Both! II](#)

[Implicit Multi-Fold Mechanisms in a Neural Network Model of the Universe](#)

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[Derivation of the Equivalence Principle in a Multi-fold Universe](#)

[Entanglement and Random Walks Concretize Time in a Multi-fold Universe](#)

[No Gravity Shield in Multi-folds Universes](#)

Gravity-like Attractions and Fluctuations between Entangled Systems?

Gravity Stabilizes Electroweak Vacuum – No Bubble of Nothing to Worry About!

Gravity Dictates the Number of Fermion Generations: 3

Strong CP Violation Tamed in The Presence of Gravity

Current Review all Publications around the Multi-fold universe

Right-handed neutrinos? Mass? Ask Gravity

Explaining Dark Matter Without New Physics?

Explaining Dark Energy, Small Cosmological Constant and Inflation Without New Physics?

Alignments and Gaps Between Multi-fold Universes And Loop Quantum Gravity

Ultimate Unification: Gravity-led Democracy vs. Uber-Symmetries

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Dualities or Analogies between Superstrings and Multi-fold Universes

Progress on Proving the Mass gap for Yang Mills and Gravity (Maybe it's already proven...)

Gravity Induced Anomalies Smearing in Standard Model so that Protons May Never Decay.

Except in Black Holes

Quantum Gravity Emergence from Entanglement in a Multi-Fold Universe

References

- [1]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), "The Multi-fold theory repository, Zenodo repository," , <https://zenodo.org/communities/multi-fold-theory/>, April 1, 2023.
- [2]: viXra, (2023), "Stephane H. Maes on viXra", https://vixra.org/author/stephane_h_maes. Retrieved on April 1, 2023.
- [3]: OSF.io, (2023), "Stephane H. Maes on OSF.io", osf.io/qdaj9 and <https://osf.io/rk3vj/>. Retrieved on April 1, 2023.
- [4]: Stephane Maes, (2020-23), "Web Site Tracking all Publications around the Multi-fold universe", Navigation page listing all papers. <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/shmaes-physics-site-navigation/>.